

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SANOUSI****FIRST NAME: FADILA****PROGRAM CODE: DILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following statements about plagiarism is true?

- Plagiarism is acceptable as long as it is not detected.
- Using another author's words without proper reference.¹**
- Paraphrasing without giving credit is allowed.
- Only direct quotes need to be cited.

¹ Laurent Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th edition (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 33–39.

2. Which form is preferred if you cite the same source multiple times?
- Full citation each.
 - 'Ibid.' for repeated references.**²
 - Abbreviated title for repeated references.
 - No reference is needed after the first.
3. What is the role of a research question in a thesis?
- To provide a brief summary of the entire study.
 - To replace the hypothesis entirely.
 - To guide the research and focus the scope of the study.**³
 - To provide definitions of key terms.
4. What is recommended when using quotations of four or more lines?
- Italicise the quote.
 - Use quotation marks.
 - Format a block quote.**⁴
 - Use single spacing.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations : Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 17th edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 172.

³ Turabian, 21–23.

⁴ Turabian, 328.

5. What is the purpose of using introductory signals in legal citations?
- To indicate the volume number of a source.
 - To show the relationship between the cited authority and the proposition.**⁵
 - To provide the publication year of a source.
 - To list the authors of a source.
6. What is serendipity in research?
- Random sampling techniques.
 - Unexpected findings lead to new insights.**⁶
 - Statistical reliability checks.
 - Pre-determined research hypotheses.
7. What is the primary purpose of a literature review?
- To summarise all existing research on a topic.
 - To critique prior studies.
 - To identify gaps in research and position your study.**⁷
 - To present research results.

⁵ Mary Miles Prince, ed., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th edition (Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 55–56.

⁶ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd edition (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 15-16, 54.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations : Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 95–99.

8. What is the key difference between American and British English that the coursepack emphasises?
- American English uses more commas than British English.
 - American English uses double quotation marks, while British English prefers single quotation marks.**⁸
 - British English avoids punctuation altogether.
 - British English allows sentence fragments, while American English does not.
9. Which element ensures the credibility of qualitative measures?
- Relevance.**⁹
 - Face validity.
 - Reliability scores.
 - Standardisation.
10. What is the significance of using parenthetical information in citations?
- To provide the page number of the source.
 - To indicate the publication date of the source.
 - To list the authors of the source.
 - To explain the relevance of the cited authority.**¹⁰

⁸ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 24–32.

⁹ Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 42.

¹⁰ Prince, *The Bluebook*, 57–58.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.